

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract

This article examines the role of additive technologies, or 3D printing, in the modern production process and the formation of key industries. The key areas of application for these technologies, including medicine, construction, and the automotive and aviation industries, are examined. It also analyzes how additive technologies can have an impact on the economy and urban infrastructure, with an emphasis on the example of the city of Aktobe.

Keywords: additive technologies, 3D printing, traditional manufacturing, additive manufacturing, bioprinting, industry, urbanization, economy.

Introduction

In the rapidly changing world of manufacturing, additive technologies, often referred to as additive manufacturing or 3D printing, have become transformative aspects, transforming manufacturing processes globally. By manufacturing objects layer by layer based on digital models, these technologies provide an unprecedented level of design flexibility, customization and effectiveness. Unlike traditional production methods, additive technologies make it possible to reduce production costs and increase the flexibility of production processes, creating products of high complexity with minimal waste [1]. This opportunity is of great importance for a variety of industries, including aerospace, medical, automotive and construction.

As a key industrial center of Western Kazakhstan, Aktobe is beginning to realize the potential of additive technologies to expand its production capabilities and stimulate economic diversification. This article examines the global impact of additive technologies, raises the question of their advantages over traditional production methods, as well as their implementation and future potential in Aktobe. Analyzing the problems and

opportunities, it is considered how Aktobe can use additive manufacturing to stimulate technological progress and economic growth.

Global Impact of Additive Technologies

Additive manufacturing has revolutionized numerous industries:

1. Industrial production.

3D printing technologies are widely applied in various industries, including mechanical engineering and aircraft engineering. In these industries, additive technologies are used to create complex elements that are difficult or expensive to manufacture using traditional methods [2]. Companies like Airbus and GE Aviation adopted 3D printing to manufacture complex engine components and aircraft parts. This method reduces weight and fuel consumption while also improving performance. To exemplify, Ge LEAP engine fuel nozzle, traditionally made from 20 parts, is now produced as a single 3D-printed piece, leading to weight reduction and improved durability (pic. 1). In addition to industrial applications, additive technologies have had a profound impact on healthcare.

Pic. 1 Additive technologies in industry

2. Healthcare.

One of the key areas of application of additive technologies is medicine. With the help of 3D printers, it is possible to manufacture prostheses and implants, as well as create accurate models of organs to prepare for surgical operations (pic. 2, pic. 3) [3]. In the future,

bioprinting is expected to allow the creation of organs and tissues for transplantation, which will make revolutionary changes in medicine and significantly expand the possibilities of treating complex diseases [4].

Pic. 2 Testing and development of spinal implants

Pic. 3 3D printing of a heart bioprosthesis

3. Construction.

Additive technologies are also developing rapidly in the construction industry, where they open up new prospects for rapid and economical construction of buildings (pic. 4) [5]. Thanks to 3D printers, residential building projects have already been implemented in countries such as China and the UAE. This technology

can significantly reduce construction time, as well as reduce the cost of materials and labor, which makes it promising for solving housing problems in areas with limited resources. These innovations demonstrate how additive technologies revolutionize multiple industries, paving the way for further advancements in fields such as healthcare, construction, and beyond.

Pic. 4 Construction of a building using additive technologies

Advantages of Additive Technologies

Additive technologies significantly affect different areas of production. These technologies allow you to recreate objects by adding material in stages based on a digital model. Unlike traditional production methods, additive technologies provide a number of exceptional advantages that make them in demand in the modern world [6].

Cost Reduction in Production

One of the main advantages of additive technologies is the possibility of significantly reducing production costs. This is due to several factors:

- **Less waste.** In traditional manufacturing processes such as milling or turning, a certain proportion of materials are often wasted. In additive technologies, only the appropriate amount of material is used to manufacture the product, which minimizes the amount of waste (pic. 5, pic. 6).

Pic. 5 Traditional manufacturing

Pic. 6 Additive manufacturing

- **Reducing the cost of instrumental equipment.** Traditional methods require expensive tools and molds, especially in large-scale production. Additive technologies, on the contrary, make it possible to do without such costs, since products are created directly using digital models.

- **Savings on transportation and storage.** 3D printing ensures the production of parts directly, which reduces the need for long-term transportation and storage of large batches of products.

Acceleration of the production process

Additive technologies can significantly reduce the time to create the final product:

- **Rapid prototyping.** One of the main advantages of 3D printing is the ability to create prototypes instantly. While traditional methods can take weeks to create a working prototype, 3D printers can do it in a matter of hours or days.

- **Optimization of development time.** Engineers can test and upgrade their developments faster, which speeds up the product's entry into the market. This gives companies a significant competitive advantage.

Reducing environmental impact

Additive technologies also play a significant role in reducing the negative impact on the environment:

- **Waste minimization.** As already mentioned, 3D printing allows you to apply exactly as much material as is necessary to create a product. This reduces waste and reduces resource consumption.

- **The use of environmentally friendly materials.** Additive technologies can use more environmentally friendly materials, such as bioplastics, which are easier to recycle or decompose.

- **Reduction of transportation costs.** The production of products closer to the place of use reduces the amount of harmful emissions associated with the transportation of goods.

Table 1

Comparison of Traditional Manufacturing vs. Additive Manufacturing

Factor	Traditional manufacturing	Additive manufacturing
Material waste	Up to 70% waste in machining processes	Less than 10% waste due to precise material usage [6]
Customization cost	High cost for custom designs due to tooling changes	Low cost (easy customization from digital models) [1]
Product lead time	Weeks to months for tooling and setup	Hours to days for design to production [2]
Complexity of designs	Limited by tooling capabilities	High complexity achievable without additional cost [3]
Inventory requirements	Requires large inventory storage	On-demand production reduces inventory needs [5]

For example: To illustrate the advantages of additive manufacturing, consider the production of a component weighing 1 kg using both traditional and additive methods.

Traditional Manufacturing:

Material Required: Approximately 3 kg (due to material removed during machining)

Material Waste: 3 kg - 1 kg = 2 kg waste

Additive Manufacturing:

Material Required: Approximately 1,1 kg (including support structures)

Material Waste: 1,1 kg - 1 kg = 0,1 kg waste

Material Savings:

Waste Reduction: 2 kg (traditional) – 0,1 kg (additive) = 1,9 kg less waste

Percentage Reduction: $(1,9 \text{ kg} / 2 \text{ kg}) * 100\% = 95\%$ reduction in material waste

Additive Technologies in Aktobe

Pic. 7 Using a 3D printer in the construction of buildings

In addition, the introduction of additive technologies into the medical field of Aktobe will open up new opportunities for the creation of affordable medical prostheses and implants, which will help reduce dependence on foreign medical devices and increase the availability of modern medical technologies.

Aktobe can also become a center of production using 3D technologies in Kazakhstan, due to its favorable location and developed infrastructure. This will help attract investments in high-tech industries and create new jobs, which will have a positive impact on the economy of the city and the region as a whole. Thus, Aktobe is positioned to harness additive technologies, potentially establishing itself as a leading hub in high-tech manufacturing in Kazakhstan.

Future Prospects

The continued investment in additive technologies could significantly impact Aktobe's economic development. By fostering collaboration between government, industry, and academia, the city can:

- Encourage innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Attract foreign investment and partnerships.

Being an important economic and industrial center of Kazakhstan, Aktobe stand to gain significant benefits through the introduction of additive technologies in various industries. Especially 3D printing technologies can play a key role in the construction of affordable housing for the rapidly growing population of the city. This is particularly important in the context of growing urbanization and increasing demand for affordable housing.

Additive technologies can also contribute to the improvement of urban infrastructure, for example, in the production of innovative materials for road construction or in the creation of small architectural forms for urban improvement. The use of 3D printers for the production of these elements will reduce costs and improve the quality of construction, as well as reduce the time for project implementation (pic. 7).

- Enhance the competitiveness of local industries on a global scale.

Conclusion

Additive technologies are already having a significant impact on various industries, revealing new prospects for improving production processes and accelerating innovative development. Thanks to these technologies, it is possible to significantly reduce costs, increase the environmental friendliness of production and speed up the time of product launch to the market.

The gradual introduction of these technologies in Aktobe reflects the desire for modernization and economic growth. By addressing challenges and capitalizing on opportunities, additive manufacturing can become the cornerstone of Aktobe's industrial landscape, stimulating innovation and increasing competitiveness.

References

1. Campbell T., Williams C., Ivanova O., Garrett B. (2011). Could 3D Printing Change the World? Technologies, Potential, and Implications of Additive Manufacturing. Atlantic Council, 6-7.

2. Hao B., Lin G. (2020). 3D printing technology and its application in industrial manufacturing, 3-4.
3. Gibson I., Rosen D., Stucker B. (2015). Additive Manufacturing Technologies: 3D Printing, Rapid Prototyping, and Direct Digital Manufacturing (2nd ed.), 43.
4. Mills D. K. (2015). Future Medicine: The Impact of 3D Printing, 2.
5. Campbell I., Diegel O., Kowen J., Mostow N., Wohlers T. (2021). Wohlers Associates. Wohlers Report 2021: Additive Manufacturing and 3D Printing State of the Industry, 90.
6. Voropaev S. S., Kozlov A. A., Kiryushchenko E. V. (2023) Advantages of additive technologies on the example of 3D printing of molds, 73-74.